

Indexed Absolute Riesz Summability Factor Using Delta Quasi Monotone Sequence

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Abstract.

A result concerning absolute indexed Riesz Summability factor of an infinite series using δ -quasi monotone sequence has been established.

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1. Introduction

We ask that authors follow simple guidelines. In essence, we ask you to make your paper look exactly like this document. A sequence (a_n) of positive numbers is said to be almost increasing if there exists a positive sequence (b_n) and two positive constants A and B such that

$$(1.1) \quad Ab_n \leq a_n \leq Bb_n, \text{ for all } n \in N.$$

It is said to be quasi- β -power increasing, if there exists a constant K depending upon β with $K \geq 1$ such that

$$(1.2) \quad K n^\beta a_n \geq m^\beta a_m,$$

for all $n \geq m$. Particularly, if $\beta = 0$, then (a_n) is a quasi-increasing sequence. It is clear that for any non-negative β , every almost increasing sequence is a quasi- β -power increasing sequence. But the converse is not true in general, as $(n^{-\beta})$ is quasi- β -power increasing but not almost increasing.

Let $f = (f_n)$ be a positive sequence of numbers. Then the positive sequence (a_n) is said to be quasi- f -power increasing, if there exists a constant K depending upon f with $K \geq 1$ such that

$$(1.3) \quad K f_n a_n \geq f_m a_m$$

for $n \geq m \geq 1$. Clearly, if (a_n) is a quasi- f -power increasing sequence, then the $(a_n f_n)$ is a quasi-increasing sequence.

Let $\delta = (\delta_n)$ be a positive sequence of numbers. Then the positive sequence (a_n) is said to be δ -quasi monotone, $a_n \rightarrow 0$, $a_n > 0$ ultimately and $\Delta d_n \geq -\delta_n$, where $\Delta d_n = d_n - d_{n-1}$.

Let $\sum a_n$ be an infinite series with sequence of partial sums $\{s_n\}$. Let (p_n) be a sequence of positive numbers such that

$$P_n = \sum_{v=0}^n p_v \rightarrow \infty, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Then the sequence-to-sequence transformation

$$(1.4) \quad T_n = \frac{1}{P_n} \sum_{v=0}^n p_v s_v, \quad P_n \neq 0,$$

defines the $(\overline{N}, p_n)$ -mean of the sequence (s_n) generated by the sequence of coefficients (p_n) . The series $\sum a_n$ is said to be summable $\left| \overline{N}, p_n \right|_k$, $k \geq 1$, if

$$(1.5) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n} \right)^{k-1} |T_n - T_{n-1}|^k < \infty.$$

The series $\sum a_n$ is said to be summable $\left| \overline{N}, p_n; \delta \right|_k$, $k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$, if

$$(1.6) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n} \right)^{\delta k + k - 1} |T_n - T_{n-1}|^k < \infty.$$

The series $\sum a_n$ is said to be summable $\left| \overline{N}, p_n, \alpha_n(\delta) \right|_k$, $k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$, if

$$(1.7) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\alpha_n)^k \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n} \right)^{k-1} |T_n - T_{n-1}|^k < \infty.$$

For any real number μ , the series $\sum a_n$ is said to be summable by the summability method $\left| \overline{N}, p_n, \alpha_n(\delta), \mu \right|_k$, $k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$, if

$$(1.8) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{\mu(k-1)} |T_n - T_{n-1}|^k < \infty :$$

For $\mu = 1$, the summability method $|\bar{N}, p_n, \alpha_n(\delta), \mu|_k, k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$, reduces to the method $|\bar{N}, p_n, \alpha_n(\delta)|_k, k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$,

2. Known Theorems

Dealing with quasi- f - power increasing sequence, Palo et al[4] prove the following theorem.

2.1. Theorem

Let $f = (f_n) = (n^\beta (\log n)^\gamma)$ be a sequence and (X_n) be a quasi- f -power sequence.

Let (λ_n) a sequence of constants such that

$$(2.1.1) \quad \lambda_n \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty,$$

$$(2.1.2) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n X_n |\Delta| |\Delta \lambda_n| < \infty$$

$$(2.1.3) \quad |\lambda_n| X_n = O(1),$$

$$(2.1.4) \quad \sum_{n=v+1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)} \frac{1}{P_{n-1}^k} = O\left(\left(\alpha_m\right)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_m}{p_m}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)}\right),$$

$$(2.1.5) \quad \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)} \frac{|t_n|^k}{X_n^{k-1}} = O(X_m),$$

$$(2.1.6) \quad \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)} \frac{|t_n|^k}{n X_n^{k-1}} = O(X_m),$$

where (t_n) is the n th $(C,1)$ mean of the sequence $(n a_n)$.

Then the series $\sum a_n \lambda_n$ is summable $|\bar{N}, p_n, \alpha_n(\delta)|_k, k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$.

Dealing with quasi- δ - quasi monotone sequence, Sarangi et al. [4] Proved the following theorem:

2.2. Theorem

Let $f = (f_n) = (n^\beta (\log n)^\gamma)$ be a sequence and (X_n) be a quasi- f -power sequence. Suppose also that there exists a sequence of numbers (A_n) such that it is δ - quasi - monotone with

$$(2.2.1) \quad \sum n \delta_n X_n < \infty$$

$$(2.2.2) \quad \Delta A_n \leq \delta_n \quad \text{for all } n.$$

Let (λ_n) a sequence of constants such that

$$(2.2.3) \quad \lambda_n \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty,$$

$$(2.2.4) \quad |\lambda_n|X_n = O(1),$$

and

$$(2.2.5) \quad |\Delta\lambda_n| \leq |A_n| \text{ for all } n.$$

Then the series $\sum a_n \lambda_n$ is summable $|\bar{N}, p_n; \sigma, \mu|_k, k \geq 1, \sigma \geq 0$, if

$$(2.2.6) \quad \sum_{n=\nu+1}^m \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{\sigma k-1} \frac{1}{P_{n-1}} = O\left(\frac{P_\nu}{p_\nu}\right)^{\sigma k-1},$$

$$(2.2.7) \quad \sum_{n=1}^m \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{\mu(\sigma k+k-1)-k} \frac{|t_n|^k}{X_n^{k-1}} = O(X_m),$$

$$(2.2.8) \quad \sum_{n=1}^m \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{\mu(\sigma k+k-1)-k+1} \frac{|t_n|^k}{nX_n^{k-1}} = O(X_m),$$

where (t_n) is the n th $(C,1)$ mean of the sequence (na_n) .

However, extending to summability method $|\bar{N}, p_n, \alpha_n(\delta), \mu|_k, k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$, in this paper, we prove the following theorem.

3. Theorem

Let $f = (f_n) = (n^\beta (\log n)^\gamma)$ be a sequence and (X_n) be a quasi- f -power sequence. Suppose also that there exists a sequence of numbers (A_n) such that it is δ -quasi-monotone with

$$(3.1) \quad \sum n \delta_n X_n < \infty$$

$$(3.2) \quad \Delta A_n \leq \delta_n \text{ for all } n.$$

Let (λ_n) a sequence of constants such that

$$(3.3) \quad \lambda_n \rightarrow 0, \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty,$$

$$(3.4) \quad |\lambda_n|X_n = O(1),$$

and

$$(3.5) \quad |\Delta\lambda_n| \leq |A_n| \text{ for all } n.$$

$$(3.6) \quad \sum_{n=\nu+1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{1}{P_{n-1}^k} = O\left(\left(\alpha_\nu\right)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_\nu}{p_\nu}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1}\right),$$

$$(3.7) \quad \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{|t_n|^k}{X_n^{k-1}} = O(X_m),$$

$$(3.8) \quad \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)} \frac{|t_n|^k}{nX_n^{k-1}} = O(X_m),$$

where (t_n) is the n th $(C,1)$ mean of the sequence (na_n) .

Then the series $\sum a_n \lambda_n$ is summable $\left[\bar{N}, p_n, \alpha_n(\delta) \right]_k, k \geq 1, \delta \geq 0$.

In order to prove the theorem we require the following lemma.

4. Lemma

Let $f = (f_n) = (n^\beta (\log n)^\gamma), 0 \leq \beta < 1, \gamma \geq 0$ be a sequence and (X_n) be a quasi- f -power increasing sequence. Let (A_n) be a sequence of numbers such that it is δ -quasi-monotone satisfying (3.1) and (3.2). then

$$(4.1) \quad n X_n |A_n| = O(1)$$

and

$$(4.2) \quad \sum_{n=1}^m X_n |A_n| < \infty, \text{ as } m \rightarrow \infty.$$

4.1. Proof Of The Lemma

As $A_n \rightarrow 0$ and $n^\beta (\log n)^\gamma X_n$ is non-decreasing, we have

$$\begin{aligned} n X_n |A_n| &= n^{1-\beta} (\log n)^{-\gamma} \left(n^\beta (\log n)^\gamma X_n \right) \sum_{v=n}^{\infty} \Delta |A_v| \\ &= O(1) n^{1-\beta} (\log n)^\gamma n \sum_{v=n}^{\infty} v^\beta (\log v)^\gamma X_v |\Delta A_v| \\ &= O(1) \sum_{v=n}^{\infty} v^{1-\beta} (\log v)^{-\gamma} v^\beta (\log v)^\gamma X_v |\Delta A_v| \\ &= O(1) \sum_{v=n}^{\infty} v X_v |\Delta A_v|. \\ &= O(1) \sum_{v=n}^{\infty} v X_v |\delta_v| \\ &= O(1) \end{aligned}$$

This establishes (4.1).

Next

$$\sum_{n=1}^m X_n |A_n| = \sum_{n=1}^{m-1} \left(\sum_{r=1}^n X_r \right) \Delta |A_n| + |A_m| \left(\sum_{r=1}^m X_r \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= O(1) \sum_{n=1}^{m-1} \left(\sum_{r=1}^n r^{-\beta} (\log r)^{-\gamma} r^{\beta} (\log r)^{\gamma} X_r \right) \Delta |A_n| \\
 &\quad + O(1) \left(\sum_{r=1}^m r^{-\beta} (\log r)^{-\gamma} r^{\beta} (\log r)^{\gamma} X_r \right) |A_m| \\
 &= O(1) \sum_{n=1}^{m-1} \left(n^{\beta} (\log n)^{\gamma} X_n \right) \Delta |A_n| \sum_{r=1}^n r^{-\beta-\epsilon} (\log r)^{-\gamma} r^{\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + O(1) m^{\beta} X_m |A_m| (\log m)^{\gamma} \sum_{r=1}^m r^{-\beta-\epsilon} (\log r)^{-\gamma} r^{\epsilon}, \epsilon < 1 - \beta. \\
 &= O(1) \sum_{n=1}^{m-1} \left(n^{\beta} (\log n)^{\gamma} X_n \right) \Delta |A_n| n^{\epsilon} (\log n)^{-\gamma} \sum_{r=1}^n r^{-\beta-\epsilon} \\
 &\quad + O(1) m^{\beta} X_m |A_m| (\log m)^{\gamma} m^{\epsilon} (\log m)^{-\gamma} \sum_{r=1}^m r^{-\beta-\epsilon} \\
 &= O(1) \sum_{n=1}^m n^{\beta+\epsilon} X_n \Delta |A_n| \left(\int_1^n u^{-\beta-\epsilon} du \right) + O(1) m^{\beta+\epsilon} X_m |A_m| \left(\int_1^m u^{-\beta-\epsilon} du \right) \\
 &= O(1) \sum_{n=1}^m n X_n \Delta |A_n| + O(1) m X_m |A_m| \\
 &= O(1) .
 \end{aligned}$$

This establishes (4.2).

5. Proof Of The Theorem

Let (T_n) be the sequence of $(\overline{N}, p_n)$ mean of the series $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \lambda_n$, then

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_n &= \frac{1}{P_n} \sum_{\nu=0}^n p_{\nu} \sum_{r=0}^{\nu} a_r \lambda_r \\
 &= \frac{1}{P_n} \sum_{\nu=0}^n (P_n - P_{\nu-1}) a_{\nu} \lambda_{\nu}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence for $n \geq 1$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_n - T_{n-1} &= \frac{P_n}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{\nu=1}^n P_{\nu-1} a_{\nu} \lambda_{\nu} \\
 &= \frac{P_n}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{\nu=1}^n \nu a_{\nu} \left(\frac{1}{\nu} P_{\nu-1} \lambda_{\nu} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{(n+1)}{n} \frac{P_n}{P_n} t_n \lambda_n + \frac{P_n}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} P_{\nu-1} t_{\nu} \lambda_{\nu} \frac{\nu+1}{\nu} + \frac{P_n}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} P_{\nu} t_{\nu} \frac{\nu+1}{\nu} \Delta \lambda_{\nu} + \frac{P_n}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} P_{\nu} t_{\nu} \frac{\lambda_{\nu+1}}{\nu}$$

$$= T_{n1} + T_{n2} + T_{n3} + T_{n4} \text{ (say).}$$

In order to prove the theorem ,using Minkowski's inequality it is enough to show that

$$\sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n} \right)^{\mu(k-1)} |T_{nj}| < \infty, j = 1,2,3,4.$$

Applying Hölder's inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n} \right)^{\mu(k-1)} |T_{n,1}|^k \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n} \right)^{\mu(k-1)} \left| \frac{(n+1)}{n} \frac{P_n}{P_n} t_n \lambda_n \right|^k \\ &= O(1) \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n} \right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{|t_n|^k}{X_n^{k-1}} \left(X_n |\lambda_n| \right)^{k-1} |\lambda_n| \\ &= O(1) \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n} \right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{|t_n|^k}{X_n^{k-1}} |\lambda_n| \\ &= O(1) \sum_{n=1}^{m-1} \left(\sum_{\nu=1}^n (\alpha_{\nu})^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_{\nu}}{p_{\nu}} \right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{|t_{\nu}|^k}{X_{\nu}^{k-1}} \right) \Delta |\lambda_n| \\ &\quad + O(1) \left(\sum_{\nu=1}^m (\alpha_{\nu})^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_{\nu}}{p_{\nu}} \right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{|t_{\nu}|^k}{X_{\nu}^{k-1}} \right) |\lambda_m| \\ &= O(1) \sum_{n=1}^{m-1} X_n |A_n| + O(1) X_m |\lambda_m| \\ &= O(1) \end{aligned}$$

Next,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{\mu(k-1)} |T_{n,2}|^k \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{\mu(k-1)} \left| \frac{p_n}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} p_{\nu-1} t_{\nu} \lambda_{\nu} \frac{(\nu+1)}{\nu} \right|^k \\
 &= O(1) \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{1}{P_{n-1}} \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} p_{\nu-1} |t_{\nu}|^k |\lambda_{\nu}|^k \left(\frac{1}{P_{n-1}} \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} p_{\nu} \right)^{k-1} \\
 &= O(1) \sum_{\nu=1}^m p_{\nu-1} |t_{\nu}|^k |\lambda_{\nu}|^k \sum_{n=\nu+1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{1}{P_{n-1}} \\
 &= O(1) \sum_{\nu=1}^m (\alpha_{\nu})^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_{\nu}}{p_{\nu}}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} |t_{\nu}|^k |\lambda_{\nu}|^k \\
 &= O(1)
 \end{aligned}$$

Again,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{\mu(k-1)} |T_{n,3}|^k \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{\mu(k-1)} \left| \frac{p_n}{P_n P_{n-1}} \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} p_{\nu} t_{\nu} \frac{(\nu+1)}{\nu} \Delta \lambda_{\nu} \right|^k \\
 &= O(1) \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{1}{P_{n-1}^k} \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} p_{\nu}^k \frac{|t_{\nu}|^k}{X_{\nu}^{k-1}} |\Delta \lambda_{\nu}| \left(\sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} X_{\nu} |\Delta \lambda_{\nu}| \right)^{k-1} \\
 &= O(1) \sum_{\nu=1}^m p_{\nu}^k \frac{|t_{\nu}|^k}{X_{\nu}^{k-1}} |\Delta \lambda_{\nu}| \sum_{n=\nu+1}^{m+1} (\alpha_n)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{1}{P_{n-1}^k} \\
 &= O(1) \sum_{\nu=1}^m (\alpha_{\nu})^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_{\nu}}{p_{\nu}}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)} \frac{|t_{\nu}|^k}{\nu X_{\nu}^{k-1}} (\nu |\Delta \lambda_{\nu}|) \\
 &= O(1) \left(\sum_{\nu=1}^{m-1} \left(\sum_{r=1}^{\nu} (\alpha_r)^{k\mu} \left(\frac{P_r}{p_r}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)} \frac{|t_r|^k}{r X_r^{k-1}} \right) (\nu |\Delta \lambda_{\nu}|) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$+ O(1)\left(m|\Delta\lambda_m|\right)\sum_{r=1}^m (\alpha_r)^{k\mu}\left(\frac{P_r}{p_r}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)}$$

$$= O(1)\sum_{\nu=1}^{m-1} X_\nu(-|\Delta\lambda_\nu| + (\nu+1)|\Delta||\Delta\lambda_\nu|) + O(1)mX_m|\Delta\lambda_m|$$

$$= O(1)$$

Finally,

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu}\left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{\mu(k-1)} |T_{n,4}|^k \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu}\left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{\mu(k-1)} \left| \frac{p_n}{P_n} \frac{n-1}{p_{n-1}} \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} p_\nu t_\nu \frac{\lambda_{\nu+1}}{\nu} \right|^k \\ &= O(1)\sum_{n=1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu}\left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{1}{P_{n-1}^k} \sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} \frac{p_\nu}{\nu} |t_\nu|^k |\lambda_\nu|^k \left(\sum_{\nu=1}^{n-1} \frac{p_\nu}{\nu}\right)^{k-1} \\ &= O(1)\sum_{\nu=1}^m \frac{p_\nu}{\nu} |t_\nu|^k |\lambda_\nu|^k \sum_{n=\nu+1}^m (\alpha_n)^{k\mu}\left(\frac{P_n}{p_n}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)-1} \frac{1}{P_{n-1}} \\ &= O(1)\sum_{\nu=1}^m (\alpha_\nu)^{k\mu}\left(\frac{P_\nu}{p_\nu}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)} \frac{|t_\nu|^k}{\nu X_\nu^{k-1}} (X_\nu |\lambda_\nu|)^{k-1} |\lambda_\nu| \\ &= O(1)\sum_{\nu=1}^{m-1} \left\{ \sum_{r=1}^{\nu} (\alpha_r)^{k\mu}\left(\frac{P_r}{p_r}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)} \frac{|t_r|^k}{r X_r^{k-1}} \right\} |\Delta\lambda_\nu| \\ & \quad + O(1)\sum_{r=1}^m (\alpha_r)^{k\mu}\left(\frac{P_r}{p_r}\right)^{(\mu-1)(k-1)} \frac{|t_r|^k}{r X_r^{k-1}} \\ &= O(1)\sum_{\nu=1}^{m-1} X_\nu |\Delta\lambda_\nu| + O(1)mX_m |\Delta\lambda_m| \\ &= O(1). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of the theorem.

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